

Reading MUMPS at Scale: An Open Parser and an Empirical Study of VistA

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Abstract—We present an open, analysis-oriented parser for MUMPS, implemented as a tree-sitter grammar, and validate it on the largest open MUMPS codebase: it parses 98.6% of VistA’s 33,951 routines with no error nodes. VistA is the electronic health record long deployed across US Department of Veterans Affairs hospitals and, as of 2026, still in production at roughly 160 of about 170 VA medical facilities as a phased migration to a commercial system proceeds, and it is written in MUMPS, a programming language from the 1970s. Every engine that executes MUMPS contains a parser (InterSystems IRIS/Caché, GT.M, YottaDB), but those parsers are built for execution, the dominant commercial one is proprietary, and none exposes a publicly reusable syntax tree for analysis tooling. We use the parser to measure two properties of VistA. Its structure is hub-and-spoke: of 155,354 inter-routine call edges, the two shared foundations, FileMan and Kernel, absorb 35.5% and the ten highest-fan-in routines 28.8%, and 122 of the 137 packages that issue calls reach both foundations. Its use of runtime code generation bounds what static analysis can recover from the source alone: indirection appears in 51.1% of routines and the XECUTE command in 29.8%, and 95.6% of the 20,689 XECUTE sites take a runtime-computed argument (a variable, expression, or concatenation) rather than a literal constant at the call site. We release the grammar, the analysis tooling, and the derived dataset for reproduction and reuse on any standard-M system.

Index Terms—MUMPS, VistA, electronic health records, parsing, tree-sitter, static analysis, legacy software

I. INTRODUCTION

VistA (Veterans Health Information Systems and Technology Architecture) has run the clinical operations of US Department of Veterans Affairs hospitals for about forty years and, as of 2026, remained in production at roughly 160 of about 170 VA medical facilities as a phased migration to a commercial system proceeds [10]. It is one of the largest and longest-lived production electronic health record (EHR) systems in the world, and it is written almost entirely in MUMPS (Massachusetts General Hospital Utility Multi-Programming System), also called M: a language designed in the 1960s and 1970s for hierarchical-database programming on the hardware of that era. MUMPS has no reserved words, no operator precedence, and pervasive runtime code generation. These properties suited terse interactive programming on constrained machines, and they make the language difficult to read with the static-analysis tooling common elsewhere in software.

Every implementation that executes MUMPS contains a parser, including the commercial InterSystems IRIS/Caché and the open compilers GT.M and YottaDB [5]. These are execution parsers: embedded in language runtimes, with the

dominant commercial one closed-source, and none exposes a publicly reusable, error-tolerant concrete syntax tree of the kind that developer tooling such as linters, editors, code-navigation systems, and static analyzers is built on. Commercial MUMPS static-analysis tooling exists but is closed-source, so its grammar and results cannot be inspected or reused. The one open grammar, an ANTLR grammar in the `grammars-v4` collection, is not evaluated against real code at scale and, as Section IX discusses, parses expressions with the wrong associativity.

A research community cannot study one of the largest legacy codebases in healthcare, or any other large MUMPS system, without first reading it programmatically, and the empirical software-engineering and mining-software-repositories literature [8] has largely passed MUMPS by for want of an open parser that produces an analyzable tree. The language features behind the parsing difficulty, runtime-built program text and runtime-resolved names, also bound static analysis: a read-only pass is incomplete wherever control flow or a data target is computed at runtime, so measuring how much of a real corpus those constructs govern is a prerequisite for trusting any static result.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- 1) An open, corpus-validated MUMPS parser, a tree-sitter grammar with an external scanner, parsing 98.6% of VistA’s 33,951 routines cleanly and reusable on any standard-M system (Section III).
- 2) An empirical account of VistA’s structure as a hub-and-spoke call graph (Sections V and VI).
- 3) A measurement of VistA’s use of runtime code generation, the prevalence and syntactic shape of XECUTE arguments and indirection sites (Section VII).

We release the grammar, the external scanner, the analysis queries, and the derived datasets so that every number below can be reproduced and the instrument reused.

II. BACKGROUND: MUMPS AND VISTA

A. The language

MUMPS is a line-oriented, dynamically typed, string-centric language with an integrated hierarchical database. A program is a set of *routines* (one per file, with a `.m` extension in the corpus), each a sequence of lines. A line is either a *label* (an entry point at column 0) or an indented sequence of commands. Commands are abbreviated aggressively in practice: in the

corpus the single-letter forms `S`, `W`, and `Q` outnumber their spelled-out `SET`, `WRITE`, and `QUIT` by more than fifty to one. The properties below each bear on parsing.

No reserved words. Command names are not reserved; `SET`, `IF`, `KILL`, and `QUIT` are all valid label names, and the corpus contains real labels named after commands. Whether a token is a command is decided by its position, the start of a line or statement, not by the word itself.

No operator precedence. MUMPS evaluates all binary operators with equal precedence, strictly left to right. `2+3*4` evaluates to 20, not 14; parentheses are the only way to override evaluation order. This differs from C-family languages, and a parser that gets it wrong changes the meaning of expressions rather than producing a parse error.

The argumentless-command rule. A space after a command may introduce its argument or separate it from the next command on the same line; an argumentless command that is followed by another command on the line is separated by *two* spaces. Multi-command lines are common (over half a million in the corpus), so this boundary rule must be handled precisely.

Postconditionals as primary control flow. Any command may carry a postcondition, written `CMD:cond` with no intervening space, executing only if the condition is true. This command-level conditional has no direct C-family analog and is used heavily; the corpus contains 418,885 of them. The colon is overloaded, also appearing in `$SELECT` pairs, `FOR` loop bounds, `READ` timeouts, and device parameters, so it must be disambiguated by grammatical site.

Indirection. The `@` operator dereferences a string as program syntax: a name, a subscript, an argument list, or an entry reference can be held in a variable and resolved only at runtime. `D @X` calls the routine named by the value of `X`; `S @Y=1` assigns to the variable named by `Y`.

XECUTE. The `XECUTE` command (abbreviated `X`) takes a string and executes it as MUMPS code. It is the language's general runtime-code-generation primitive.

Globals. Persistent data is stored in *globals*, sparse hierarchical arrays named with a leading caret (`^`). Records are conventionally encoded as delimited strings within a global node and accessed field by field with `$PIECE`; the corpus contains 416,916 global reference sites.

B. VistA and the corpus

In real code these idioms co-occur. A single line can carry multiple commands, each with its own postcondition, mixing literal and indirect references; block structure is leading-dot indentation rather than delimiters; and the same punctuation (`:`, `^`, `()`) takes several syntactic roles fixed only by grammatical site. The line below, abridged from the corpus style, exercises most of these at once:

```
D:$D(^DGPM(DO)) @TAG^@RTN Q:'X
```

Here `D:$D(...)` is a postconditioned `DO` that runs only if a global node exists; `@TAG^@RTN` is a doubly indirect entry reference whose label and routine are both computed at

runtime and therefore invisible to the static call graph; and `Q:'X` is a postconditioned argumentless `QUIT` whose two-space separation from the preceding command is what tells the parser the `DO` took no further argument. A parser that does not get all three right will either mis-split the line or mis-resolve the control flow.

VistA is organized into roughly 140 *packages*, functional namespaces such as patient registration, laboratory, pharmacy, and the menu/security subsystem, layered on two shared foundations: FileMan, the data-dictionary and database engine, and Kernel, the system-services library (date/time, device handling, task management, sign-on). The publicly released reference distribution is OSEHRA VistA-M [4], an open mirror of the VA's M source tree. Our corpus is that distribution at commit `b7aecb9`: 33,951 `.m` routines, 3,639,962 lines of code, across 140 package directories. It is the largest open MUMPS codebase we know of.

III. PARSING MUMPS

We implement the parser as a tree-sitter [1] grammar. Tree-sitter is an incremental, GLR-based parser-generator system that produces concrete syntax trees, tolerates errors by localizing them to small subtrees rather than failing the whole file, and supports a declarative query language for extracting structure from the tree. These properties match the analysis use case: the tree is reusable, and a malformed or dialect-specific line costs one error node rather than an unparsable file. The three subsections below each take one corpus-measured property of MUMPS and the mechanism that handles it.

A. No reserved words: positional command detection

Because command names are not reserved, position decides whether a token is a command. We do not use a tree-sitter `word` token, which would globally reserve keywords. Instead, an external scanner establishes line structure, and each command keyword is matched by an anchored, case-insensitive abbreviation pattern (so `S`, `SE`, and `SET` all match `SET`) that applies only in command position. At the start of a line (column 0) the first token is a label; after the line's indentation, or after the separator that follows a complete command, the next token is in command position and is matched against the command set, falling back to a generic command rule when no specific command matches. Inside a command's arguments the same identifier is an ordinary variable. A bare identifier that could be either a label or a variable is declared as an intentional GLR conflict so both readings are explored.

B. No operator precedence: flat expressions

We encode an expression as a flat sequence: an operand followed by zero or more (operator, operand) pairs, with no precedence tiers. The resulting tree is a sibling list that downstream tooling reads left to right, matching MUMPS evaluation order exactly. Parentheses are the only grouping construct and are represented as a parenthesized operand. Unary operators (notably `'` for logical NOT, which appears 198,164 times in the corpus, and unary minus) bind only to their

immediate operand. Getting this wrong, by giving expressions precedence tiers or by recursing right instead of left, changes the computed value of common arithmetic.

For instance, in the line

```
S X=2+3*4, Y=' Z, A=B_C
```

a precedence-aware grammar would group $3*4$ first and assign $X=14$; the MUMPS reading is strictly left to right, so $2+3$ is formed first and $X=20$. The unary `'` in `Y=' Z` negates `Z` and binds only to it, and the `_` in `A=B_C` is string concatenation at the same precedence as every other operator. The flat-sequence encoding produces one operand-and-operator sibling list per assignment, which is the structure that yields the correct left-to-right value and that downstream queries walk without re-deriving precedence.

C. The argumentless-command rule: GLR

A space after a command keyword is ambiguous between introducing an argument and separating the command from the next command on the line; the disambiguator is that an argumentless command takes two spaces before the following command. We resolve this with GLR parsing in the spirit of Tomita's algorithm [2]: both readings are pursued in parallel and the one that lets the remainder of the line parse survives. The argument-introducing single space is modeled as an immediate-boundary token so it does not collide with the inter-command separator. The same ambiguity-tolerant mechanism handles the postcondition colon, which is admitted only immediately after a command keyword and therefore never collides with the colon's other uses.

D. The external scanner

MUMPS is whitespace-significant and line-oriented in ways that cannot be expressed as context-free token regexes, so an external scanner (`src/scanner.c`) supplies the tokens that require state. The scanner emits a logical newline; a zero-width label-start token when column 0 begins a non-space identifier or digit, which is what lets a command word be a label; a level-indent token that measures leading spaces and counts the leading dots that encode dot-block nesting depth (block structure in MUMPS has no brace or begin/end delimiter and is carried entirely by leading-dot indentation, observed in the corpus to depth 14); a whole-line comment token, because the comment introducer `;` is unescaped and may appear inside what would otherwise be code; a string-literal token with the doubled-quote escape, so that operators and semicolons inside a string do not tokenize; and a data-text token for the payload of `;` lines, including the standardized patch-tag header on a routine's second line, which is data rather than a comment body. The scanner serializes its state (nesting depth, in-string and in-comment flags, line-start flag, column) so that incremental re-parse after an edit, including an edit in the middle of a string or block, resumes correctly.

E. Coverage-driven construction

We built the grammar in coverage-driven milestones, ordered by corpus frequency so that each milestone closed the

largest remaining share of source lines. The lexical spine (the external scanner, identifiers, numbers, strings, comments, labels, and the `;` data lines) closes every comment, label, and blank line and by itself accounts for a large fraction of source lines. The core data and control commands (`SET`, `DO`, `QUIT`, `IF`, `NEW`, `WRITE`, `KILL`) together with the flat expression grammar and the common intrinsic functions cover the overwhelming majority of executable statements. Successive milestones add the remaining control flow and references (`FOR`, `ELSE`, `GOTO`, extrinsic `$$` calls, special variables, pattern matching), then the dynamic constructs (indirection in its several forms, `XECUTE`, `MERGE`), and finally the I/O, transaction, and dialect tail (`READ`, `USE`, `OPEN`, `LOCK`, the transaction commands, and the `GT.M/Caché Z`-commands). Each milestone was gated on the corpus parse-rate harness before proceeding, so coverage rose monotonically and every regression was attributable to a specific rule. A small set of known-hard cases, runtime-built `XECUTE` strings, multi-level indirection (`@@VAR`, `@TAG^@RTN`), naked global references, and a handful of archaic forms, is parsed tolerantly: captured as a coarse node rather than fully structured, so that an unresolved construct costs accuracy on that sub-node without failing the surrounding line. The parser reaches 98.6% while still surfacing these constructs.

F. Validation method

We validate by parsing every routine in the corpus and counting those with zero `ERROR` or `MISSING` nodes. The primary metric is file-level success: the fraction of routines that parse entirely clean. We also bucket every error node by the leading-token signature of its line, so failures map back to the grammar rule that owns them. As a tokenization-bug guard we compare the parser's emitted construct counts against the same constructs grepped from the source; because a command can follow another on the same line, the parser counts more than a line-leading `grep` (1,210,694 `SET` commands against about 406,000 lines beginning with `S`), and the two track together as expected. Sharing the corpus, this is a consistency guard rather than an external validation. The result is $33,481/33,951 = 98.6\%$ of routines parsing with no error nodes. File-level success understates how much source is readable: tree-sitter localizes errors, and in a pinned 2,000-routine sample only 116 of 214,557 lines fall inside an `ERROR` subtree, so 99.95% of lines parse cleanly. The remaining 1.4% (470 routines) is a long tail dominated by InterSystems Caché ObjectScript, a distinct object-oriented dialect (`$$SYSTEM.Util...obj.Method()`) that is not standard M, plus a small amount of malformed source. The residual is a different dialect rather than unhandled standard-M syntax. This 98.6% rate is in-sample, since the grammar was built against this corpus; Section VIII reports an out-of-sample check on an independent codebase. The grammar parses the corpus at about 1,500 routines per second (7.1 MB/s) single-threaded, within the latency budget editor and interactive tooling require.

IV. METHOD

The corpus is the OSEHRA VistA-M reference tree [4]: 33,951 .m routines, 3,639,962 lines, in 140 package directories. We parse every routine and, using tree-sitter queries over the grammar, extract a per-routine record of the constructs that drive the rest of the paper:

- **Call targets.** Every routine named in a DO, GOTO, JOB, or \$\$ extrinsic-function reference. We treat each routine (file) as a node and each named target as a directed edge. A target is *in-corporis* if it names a routine present in the distribution and *external/unresolved* otherwise.
- **XECUTE sites.** Every XECUTE command, with its argument classified by syntactic shape (Section VII).
- **Indirection sites.** Every use of the @ operator, in name, subscript, argument, or entry-reference position.
- **Global references.** Every persistent (^) reference site.
- **Postconditions.** Every command-level :cond conditional.

The extraction is kept sound and reproducible. Every figure derives from the concrete syntax tree rather than text matching: an XECUTE site is an `xecute_command` node, not a line containing the letter X, which avoids the false positives that defeat grep-based surveys (X as a variable name or inside a string). The queries run against the public node types of the released grammar, so a third party can rerun them and obtain the same counts. Where a construct is intentionally parsed loosely, runtime-built code inside an XECUTE string, deep or chained indirection, the tree still localizes it to a single node, so the construct is counted even when its internal structure is left opaque; this is what lets the dynamic-construct counts be complete even though their targets are unresolved.

The call graph, construct catalog, and per-routine records are derived by `scripts/callgraph.py` over the analysis queries in `queries/analysis.scm`, which consume the parse trees produced by the grammar. The derived datasets (`coverage/callgraph.json`, `coverage/full.json`) are released so that every figure below can be regenerated from the corpus without re-running the surveys.

V. VISTA IS A HUB-AND-SPOKE SYSTEM

The call graph extracted from the corpus has 155,354 distinct edges over 375,671 total call sites. Of the distinct edges, 88.5% (137,529) resolve to a routine inside the corpus and 11.5% (17,825) target external or unresolved names; the in-corporis fraction is what makes the graph analyzable as a connected structure. That structure is dominated by a small core. The highest fan-in targets, the routines called from the most distinct callers, are entirely drawn from the two shared foundations described in Section II. From FileMan, DIR is called from 6,547 routines, DIC from 5,983, DIE from 5,783, and DIQ from 5,068, with DIK and DICN close behind. From Kernel, XLFDT (date/time) is called from 5,264 routines, followed by %DTC, %ZTLOAD (task management), %ZIS (device handling), XLFSTR, and XPDUTL. The %-prefixed library routines are

not shipped as files in this distribution, so the edge shares below count them as external, making the foundations' share a lower bound. The two namespaces interleave in rank, but no application package approaches their fan-in. The concentration is quantifiable: the two foundations absorb 35.5% of all distinct edges (FileMan 41,351, Kernel 13,814), the ten highest-fan-in routines absorb 28.8% and the top fifty 47.1%, while application packages call one another far more sparsely. Under an explicit threshold of at least one inter-package call edge, 132 of the 137 packages that issue any call reach FileMan and 125 reach Kernel, 122 reaching both; the few that reach neither by a direct call are small packages that typically use FileMan through its data dictionary. (Edges are `label^routine` entry references; a bare DO LABEL with no routine name contributes no edge and is excluded.) That every package depends on FileMan and Kernel follows from their documented role as the shared data-dictionary engine and system-services library, analogous to libc; the parse trees quantify how concentrated that dependence is. Because 122 of 137 calling packages reach both, a change to a FileMan or Kernel interface has system-wide reach.

The 11.5% of edges that do not resolve in-corporis are themselves informative. They fall into two groups: references to routines that the reference distribution does not ship (site-local or proprietary extensions), and edges whose target is computed and therefore cannot be named at all by a static pass, the same indirection that Section VI quantifies. The first group is a property of the distribution; the second is a property of the language and sets a hard floor on how complete any static call graph of VistA can be. The hubs are reached by ordinary, statically named DO and \$\$ references rather than by computed dispatch, so their fan-in is directly measurable from the 88.5% of in-corporis edges.

We cross-check the extracted edges against the raw source, the obvious external oracles being unavailable in machine-comparable form (OSEHRA's DOX cross-reference is a client-rendered site, and XINDEX requires a live Kernel). For the top hubs the tree-derived fan-in matches the number of distinct routines whose source mentions ^routine to within 1–3% (DIR 6,547 vs 6,608; DIE 5,783 vs 6,003; XLFDT 5,264 vs 5,315). The one large gap, DIC (5,983 vs 9,048), is consistent with the parser rather than indicating an error: ^DIC is both a routine and a FileMan global, and a grep conflates the call with the global reference where the tree separates them. This is a same-corporis consistency check, not an independent oracle (DOX and XINDEX being unavailable).

The structure has a measurable consequence. Taking each routine's applied-patch count (from its ; ; patch list) as a maintenance-churn proxy, fan-in is associated with patch count at Spearman $\rho = 0.36$ (a weak-to-moderate monotonic association) over the 21,018 routines that carry a list, and the top fan-in decile has a median of 3 patches against 1 for the rest: the central routines are also the more heavily patched ones. Figure 1 plots the heavy-tailed fan-in distribution.

Fig. 1. Routine fan-in (distinct callers) by rank, log-log. A small core of utility routines carries the graph; the distribution is heavy-tailed.

VI. STATIC ANALYSIS OF VISTA IS BOUNDED BY CONSTRUCTION

Indirection and XECUTE each make a read-only analysis of VistA a lower bound on its behavior, and the corpus shows both are pervasive.

Indirection (@). 70,180 sites across 17,358 routines, 51.1% of the corpus, compute a name, subscript, argument, or entry reference at runtime. The position determines what the indirection bounds: 30,504 sites (43%) are subscripts and 22,162 (32%) name a SET target, which a value analysis can often resolve though a syntax-only pass cannot; 4,368 (6.2%) are call-affecting (DO/GOTO/JOB entry references), and these are the sites that add edges the static call graph cannot name. The remainder occupy other argument positions.

XECUTE. The executed program text is itself data at 20,689 sites in 10,109 routines, 29.8% of the corpus.

The 4,368 call-affecting indirection sites are the ones that make the call graph a lower bound: an indirect DO @X or GOTO @L contributes an edge that exists only at runtime and that the static graph cannot name. Beyond these two constructs, the corpus contains 418,885 postconditions and 416,916 explicit ^ global reference sites (naked references, a separate construct, are not counted), the two control-flow and state mechanisms that have no direct C-family analog; Section VI-A examines what they imply for analysis.

A. Control flow without C-family analogs

Postconditions are a primary conditional mechanism, attaching directly to the command rather than wrapping a block as an IF statement does. They are about as numerous as IF commands, 418,885 postconditions to 421,636 IF commands, so they carry roughly half of the corpus’s conditional control flow; an analysis that keys on IF alone misses that half. Each postcondition is an arbitrary boolean expression evaluated immediately before its command, and because the colon that introduces it is also used in \$SELECT pairs, FOR bounds, READ timeouts, and device parameters, recovering

postconditions reliably needs the same disambiguation-by-site the grammar performs (Section III).

The 416,916 global reference sites are the other half of the state model. VistA stores persistent data as sparse hierarchical arrays whose leaf nodes hold caret- or piece-delimited record strings, read and written field by field with \$PIECE. This means that data-flow analysis cannot confine itself to local variables: a value can leave a routine by being written to a global and re-enter another routine, or the same routine later, by being read back, with no parameter passing and no edge in the call graph to mark the transfer. Globals therefore carry inter-routine data flow that the call graph does not record, so a data-flow analysis must track global reads and writes as well as calls.

VII. RUNTIME CODE GENERATION

The XECUTE prevalence reported in Section VI bounds static analysis: whether a static reader can recover what an XECUTE runs depends on whether its argument is a fixed literal or a value computed at runtime. We classify all XECUTE arguments by that distinction.

A. Syntactic shape of XECUTE arguments

Classifying all 20,689 XECUTE arguments by the syntactic shape of the argument expression gives Table I. A literal X "S Y=1" has fixed executed text, visible in the source. A computed X CMD, where CMD is a variable or expression whose value is built at runtime, executes text that is data: the source does not reveal what it will be, so a static reader cannot recover it.

TABLE I
XECUTE ARGUMENTS IN VISTA, BY SYNTACTIC SHAPE (20,689 SITES).
SHARES ARE ROUNDED AND SUM TO 100% UP TO ROUNDING.

Argument shape	Sites	Share
Runtime-computed (variable/expression)	19,545	94.5%
Computed by string concatenation	244	1.2%
Literal code constant	895	4.3%
Indirect	5	0.0%

The computed categories (19,789 sites) account for 95.6% of all XECUTE: nineteen in twenty take a runtime-computed argument rather than a constant at the call site. This is a syntactic property of the argument, not a claim that the executed text is unrecoverable: a variable assigned a literal earlier in the routine is computed at the call site yet resolvable by local analysis. To bound that effect we ran a crude intra-routine def-use pass: of the 19,545 runtime-computed sites, 8,600 take a bare local variable, and only 1,089 (12.7%) of those have a same-routine string-literal assignment, so local constant propagation would resolve at most about 6% of computed sites. The 95.6% figure is an at-site syntactic count, not materially inflated by local literals. The “computed by string concatenation” category is separated from the bare “runtime-computed” category because the concatenation sites visibly assemble the executed string at the XECUTE site with the _ operator, so the construction is locally inspectable, whereas a bare variable’s provenance is

Fig. 2. XECUTE sites per routine: the twelve highest-density packages among those with at least 20 routines. The runtime-code surface is spread across clinical packages, not confined to FileMan.

opaque and must be traced. Recovering what a given argument evaluates to in general would require interprocedural data-flow analysis, which the released parse trees make possible and which we leave to future work.

The computed sites are not concentrated in one engine. Bucketing the 19,789 computed XECUTE sites of Table I by package shows only 839 (4.2%) fall in FileMan, where dynamic field computation from the data dictionary might be expected to account for them. The rest are spread across clinical application packages: the Automated Information Collection System holds 4,761 (24%), followed by Registration (1,480), Integrated Billing (1,390), Medicine (932), Outpatient Pharmacy, Scheduling, and Lab Service in the hundreds. Runtime-code generation is thus distributed across clinical application packages rather than concentrated in the database engine (Figure 2). All measurements here were computed over the public OSEHRA VistA-M mirror [4]; no live system was accessed.

VIII. LIMITATIONS AND THREATS TO VALIDITY

The call graph is a lower bound: given the prevalence of indirection reported in Section VI, runtime-only call edges (DO @X, GOTO @L, \$\$-to-indirect targets) are unobserved by construction, so the 155,354-edge graph underestimates the true edge set. The XECUTE classification in Table I is syntactic; it identifies arguments that are computed rather than literal but does not establish what any given argument evaluates to at runtime, so the 95.6% figure measures how much executed text is runtime-computed, not what any site does. The call graph collapses each call target to its routine (file), although MUMPS calls target a `label^routine` entry point; the parser preserves the entry point, with the tree distinguishing the call label from the `routine_name`, so routine-level collapse is a reporting choice that overstates coupling and hides interface structure rather than a parser limitation, and an entry-point-level graph is a straightforward refinement. A zero-error parse does not guarantee a semantically correct tree. The “zero ERROR/MISSING nodes” metric establishes only that the input parses; for correctness we use 10 golden corpus tests (in

test/corpus) that pin the expected tree shapes for the hard constructs, flat left-to-right expressions, the two-space argumentless rule, indirection, and XECUTE, a 202-routine snapshot regression set (guarding against unintended tree changes), and a differential test of the expression grammar against YottaDB, a production MUMPS engine. We parse each expression, fold its flat operand-and-operator sequence left to right, and compare to YottaDB: 1,500 arithmetic expressions and a further 1,200 mixing the comparison, negated-comparison, and logical operators (`<` `>` `=` `'<` `'>` `'=` `&` `!`) all matched, with no parse errors (`scripts/diff_test.py`). This shows the flat, no-precedence encoding reproduces M evaluation order on the arithmetic, comparison, and logical operators tested; it does not yet cover string, pattern-match, or the full intrinsic-function set.

The 98.6% rate is in-sample, since the grammar was built in coverage-driven milestones gated on this corpus. As an out-of-sample check we parsed Kevin O’Kane’s independently written MUMPS programs (225 routines, a different author and dialect): 56.8% parse cleanly after removing a non-standard `#!/#` script wrapper that is not part of M. Localizing the first error node in each of the 97 failures, the large majority sit on O’Kane’s MDH extensions, which are not standard M: C-style `//` comments (M uses `;`), `shell` commands, `$Z` intrinsics, `&~` delimiters, and embedded SQL or GTK. Only a handful are standard-M constructs; of these we fixed indirection of a string literal (`@". . ."`), and the rest are O’Kane’s filename-style routine references (`^name.mps`) and a stray DOS end-of-file byte. The shortfall is dialect coverage, not gaps in standard M. A second large independent corpus would strengthen this. A second large independent corpus, and a per-construct root-cause of the formatting failures, would strengthen this further.

Finally, 1.4% of routines do not parse cleanly, which could in principle bias the dynamic-construct counts downward if the unparsed routines were disproportionately heavy in XECUTE or indirection; they are not, because the unparsed tail is dominated by Caché ObjectScript, a different dialect, and the XECUTE-heavy and indirection-heavy packages parse cleanly, so the dynamic-construct counts are not depressed by parse failure, and a more complete parser would, if anything, raise them.

Finally, the measured object is the public OSEHRA mirror at one commit (`b7aecb9`); production VA instances carry site-local patches and routines not in the distribution, so these figures characterize the open corpus rather than any specific deployment.

IX. RELATED WORK

MUMPS parsers and analysis. Every MUMPS runtime, InterSystems IRIS/Caché and the open compilers GT.M and YottaDB [5], contains a parser, but those are execution parsers embedded in language engines and do not expose a reusable analysis tree; the commercial ones are also closed-source. A purpose-built commercial MUMPS static-analysis tooling exists but is closed-source, so its grammar and findings cannot be inspected or reused. VistA also ships its own cross-referencer, XINDEX (Kernel’s `%INDEX`), and OSEHRA

publishes caller/callee and call-graph listings (DOX) derived from it [11]. These produce human-readable cross-reference reports rather than a reusable, language-agnostic parse tree, so they do not provide the tree-derived, argument-level structure the measurements here require.

Two open implementations parse MUMPS, but not for analysis. O’Kane’s MUMPS interpreter and MUMPS-to-C++ compiler [6] is a full open (GPL) language implementation; its expression parser (`interp-parse.cpp`) evaluates each operand inline against the interpreter’s state vector rather than building a syntax tree a separate tool could consume. eMcellent [7] is an open parser that round-trips routines, but its data model stores each command’s arguments as a single string (its documented `mArguments` field) rather than a parsed structure, so it does not provide the argument-level structure, expressions, indirection, XECUTE arguments, and call targets, that the measurements in this paper depend on; run over our corpus it processes all 33,951 routines with exact round-trip but exposes no argument-level structure. The one open grammar we found, an ANTLR MUMPS grammar in the `grammars-v4` collection, is not validated against a real codebase at scale and groups expressions in the wrong direction. Its expression rule is right-recursive, `term (op expression)*`, so a chain of binary operators associates right to left, whereas MUMPS associates left to right. On $2+3*4$ the rule yields $2+(3*4)=14$ while MUMPS gives $(2+3)*4=20$; its emitted tree, `(expression (term 2) + (expression (term 3) * (expression (term 4))))`, nests $3*4$ as the right operand. The grammar does place all binary operators at one level, which matches MUMPS’s lack of precedence; the error is associativity, not precedence. Run over our corpus it parses 3.2% (1,079/33,951) of routines without a syntax error, against our 98.6%. Our grammar instead builds a flat left-to-right operator sequence and preserves the MUMPS semantics. We are not aware of a prior open MUMPS parser that exposes an analyzable, argument-level concrete syntax tree validated at corpus scale, nor of published, parse-tree-derived structural measurements of VistA at this scale.

Parsing technology. The parser builds on tree-sitter [1], an incremental parsing system for developer tools whose GLR core descends from Tomita’s generalized LR algorithm [2]; the GLR foundation is what lets us pursue both readings of MUMPS’s argumentless-command ambiguity in parallel. The language itself follows the M standard, ISO/IEC 11756 [3], against which we cross-checked the command and expression grammar.

Tolerant and partial parsing. Capturing hard constructs as coarse nodes rather than failing the file is the strategy of island grammars and semi-parsing for legacy languages, where a precise grammar covers the constructs of interest and the remainder is boxed or skipped [9]. Tree-sitter’s error-localizing GLR gives the same tolerance without a hand-built island/water split, so a dialect-specific line costs one error node rather than an unparsable file.

Mining software repositories. Treating a large legacy codebase as a measurable artifact, extracting a call graph and

construct catalog and reporting their distributions, is in the tradition of empirical, repository-mining software engineering [8]. MUMPS has been largely absent from that literature for want of an open parser; this work provides one that exposes an analyzable, argument-level tree, with a first set of measurements.

X. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Making MUMPS machine-readable is a prerequisite for studying or securing the software that runs VA hospitals, and no open, analysis-oriented parser previously existed. We provide that capability, a tree-sitter grammar with an external scanner that parses 98.6% of VistA’s 33,951 routines cleanly, and we use it to give a first empirical picture of the system. VistA is a hub-and-spoke monolith of 155,354 call edges in which most packages depend on a small core of about ten utility namespaces. Its heavy use of runtime code generation, through indirection and XECUTE, bounds static analysis and makes the call graph a lower bound: most XECUTE sites execute a computed value rather than a constant, and over half of all routines use indirection, so a static reader cannot recover the full control flow.

The parser targets standard M, not VistA specifically, so its usefulness is not tied to this corpus: the grammar targets the standard-M language rather than VistA-specific code, so the same queries apply in principle to other standard-M systems, making the structural measurements above repeatable as a methodology; the 56% out-of-sample rate of Section VIII shows dialect extensions still need coverage work. Both the instrument and the measurements are reproducible from the released artifacts.

The open tool supports the obvious next steps. Recovery of runtime-only call edges, by partial resolution of indirection and XECUTE targets through lightweight abstract interpretation, would tighten the call graph from a floor toward completeness. And because the grammar targets standard M rather than VistA specifically, the same measurements can be run on other production MUMPS systems, allowing the structural properties reported here to be compared across codebases.

ARTIFACTS

The grammar, external scanner, analysis queries, coverage harness, call-graph tooling, golden tests, and the derived JSON datasets (`callgraph.json`, `full.json`) are released in the `tree-sitter-mumps` repository so that every result in this paper can be reproduced from the corpus and the instrument reused on other MUMPS systems.

USE OF GENERATIVE AI

Generative AI tools were used for code assistance, document formatting, and grammar. All research contributions, design decisions, experiments, and analysis are the authors’ own.

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